

A NEW SPECIES OF THE GENUS *HEMIBUTHUS* POCOCK (ARACHNIDA: SCORPIONIDA: BUTHIDAE) FROM PAKISTAN WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CHROMATOGRAPHY AND ELECTROPHORESIS OF ITS VENOM

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ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Hemibuthus* is described from Rohri Sindh, Pakistan with special reference to its male genitalia, electrophoresis and chromatography of the venom. This species is compared with its closest ally and the relationships is briefly discussed using autapomorphic characters.

Key Words: New species, *Hemibuthus*, Arachnida, Chromatography, electrophoresis.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Hemibuthus* first time described by Pocock (1900) recorded from India and Africa, later Vochon (1960) and Stahnke (1972) described the genus *Hemibuthus*. Tikader and Bastawade (1983) described *Hemibuthus* to accommodate only one species, the type *crassimanus* (Pocock) from India, Panch Mahel, Gujrat on the basis of external morphology and the appendages but they did not include the genital appendage. Study was carried out on male genitalia and chromatography and electrophoresis of venom, and on the basis of these characters the relationship is briefly discussed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The animals were collected from the Rohri Sindh Pakistan and were killed with the help of formalin and preserved in 70% alcohol. For the study of male genitalia the specimen were dissected out by removing the tergites of mesosoma. After dissection the aedeagus was mounted on slide then taken the photograph using Photographic microscope. For the study of electrophoresis and chromatography the technique generally followed by Amir *et al* (1994 a,b,c,d and 2003).

Hemibuthus umarii sp.n.
(Figs. 1-3)

Colouration:

Body generally yellow.

Prosoma:

Carapace: Entire surface of carapace smooth, all carinae smooth. ocular tubercles blackish and blackish brown, anterior margins granular and provided with 42-44 blackish brown setae, lateral margins not crenulated on anterior portion.

Pedipalp:

Manus globular, longer than femur, shorter than carapace, almost all carinae granular, outer and anterior side provided with a crenulated crest of 14-16 denticular tubercles, patella longer than femur but always longer than carapace, inner or anterior surface provided almost granular crest with 17-sub-denticular tubercles. Manus or hand globular and length of underhand longer than femur. Fixed finger almost as long as femur but movable finger

longer than carapace. Dentition on the fingers consisting of 3 rows of imbricated teeth granular on the fixed and movable finger. Trichobothrial pattern of pedipalp 'A' type.

Fig.1. *Hemibuthus umarii*; A. dorsal view, B. ventral view.

Table 1. Measurement in cm/mm meristic character of the male holotype *Hemibuthus umarii* sp.n.

Characters	Holotype (Male)
Total	length 5.2 cm.
Carapace length	0.55 cm.
Mesosoma length	1.5 cm.
Metasoma length	3.18 cm.
I segment length/width	0.58/0.30 cm.
II segment length/width	0.60/0.30 cm.
III segment length/width	0.64/0.36 cm.
IV segment length/width	0.66/0.4 cm.
V segment length/width	0.7/0.4 cm.
Telson length	0.6 cm.
Vesicle length/width	0.3/0.4 cm.
Aculeus length	0.3 cm.
Pedipalp length	1.75 cm.
Femur length/width	0.4/0.2 cm.
Patella length/width	0.45/0.25 cm.
Chela length/width	0.9/0.3 cm.
Fixed finger length	0.45 cm.
Movable finger length	0.47 cm.
Chelicera, Chela length/width	0.2/0.15 cm.
Fixed finger length	0.1 cm.
Movable finger length	0.11 cm.
Pectinal tooth count	26
Male Genitalia	1.6 mm

Fig.2. *Hemibuthus unarii*; A carapace, dorsal view; B. padipal, B₁ Femur, lateral view; B₂ same, patella, lateral view; B₃ Same, manus, lateral view; C. fore leg, lateral view; D. telson, lateral view; E. pecten, ventral view; F. operculum ventral view.

Fig.3. *Hemibuthus umarii*; A. aedeagus, lateral view; B. Electrophoresis of venom; C. Graph showing chromatography of venom.

Legs:

Femur weakly granular, patella smooth and carinae crenulated. Tibia strong with 2 tibial spurs on the legs III and IV, size 0.12 cm, tarsomere I laterally carinated and not provided with setae on dorsal and ventral margins, tarsomers II cylindrical.

Table 2. Variation in tarsomere II spine counts in *Hemibuthus umarii* sp.n. on each specimen, the spine of the left and right legs of each pair were counted.

Legs	Margin	4	5	6	7	8
I	Prolateral	7	7	5	5	4
	Retrolateral	5	7	5	4	4
II	Prolateral	9	8	4	5	5
	Retrolateral	5	4	4	7	6
III	Prolateral	7	5	5	4	7
	Retrolateral	5	4	6	4	7
IV	Prolateral	9	5	7	6	5
	Retrolateral	7	6	7	6	5

Table 3. Specimens collected from various localities in Sind.

Male	Female	Locality	Date of collection	Temp.	Humidity	Collector
-	1	Khairpur	6-12-93	30C ^o	38%	Aijaz
-	1	Gambat	7-12-93	29C ^o	25%	Aslam
1	1	Rohri	10-12-93	26C ^o	23%	Umar
-	1	Khairpur	11-12-93	25C ^o	10C ^o	Ali
4	-	Rohri	13-12-93	28C ^o	27%	Aijaz
-	1	Gambat	14-12-93	28C ^o	23%	Aslam

Pectins:

Pectin well developed and almost two times longer than wide, eight middle lamellae present, fulcra nearly triangular, basal piece with anterior margin slightly notched in the middle portion, pectinal teeth yellow with 26-teeth.

Genital operculum:

Genital operculum wider than long and sclerites slightly divided on posterior portion from which small genital papillae produced in male, sternum small and triangular.

Mesosoma:

All tergites finely granular but more granular on posterior portion of each tergite. Sternites I-IV tricarinated and each provided with slit-like stigmata for book lungs.

Metasoma:

Cauda five times as long as carapace, first segment shorter than wide, segments I-IV with crenulated dorsal carinae, dentiform on posterior portion much more elevated on segment III and IV, dorso-lateral carinae very weakly crenulated, lateral carinae weakly developed only on posterior portion of segment III-IV.

Telson:

Telson with vesicle not deep as segment V, ventral surface densely granular, ventral median crest not developed, sub-acute nodule absent, acute weakly curved, as short as vesicle.

Male genitalia:

Flagellum 0.7 mm long, elongated flagellar shape, trunk 0.6 mm long and 0.16 mm wide, trunk cylindrical, dilated at base, pedicel very flat, 0.3 mm long and 0.15 mm wide, sperm spine hook-like, sperm tube tubular, semi-sclerotized.

Materials examined:

Holotype, Male, Pakistan: Rohri, Sindh, 10.12.1993, leg. Umar Niaz, lodged at MEMUK No.139.

Paratypes: 2 females, other data same as holotype, lodged at ZMUK.

Comparative note:

This new species is most closely related to *Hemibuthus crassimannus* Pocock in having carapace without carinae, vesicle never provided with subacute spine but a weak subacute nodule but it can easily be separated from the same in having entire surface smooth, 26-pectinal teeth are present and by the other characters as noted in the description.

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of Scorpiian venom

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of Scorpiian venom were performed under denaturing condition using SDS (Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate) and B-Merisaphoethanol as denaturing agents MW-SDS-70L. Standard protein markers were used to prepare standard curve. The marker include, bovine serum albumin (66.0 KD a), egg albumin (45.0 KD a), glyceraldehyde-3-Phosphate, dehydrogenase, trypsinogen (24.0 KD a), trypsin inhibitor (20.0 KD a), and lactalbumin (14.2 KD a), *Hemibuthus* venoms few broad bands in the molecular weight range of 70.0 KDa to 10.0 KDa and 50.0 KDa to 15.0 KDa.

Gel filtration chromatography of *Hemibuthus*

Venom (1000 mg) of *Hemibuthus umarii* sp.n., was loaded on sephadex G-50 column (2.5 x 9000 cm) and eluted with O.I.M. ammonium acetate buffer (PH 6.90). The venom was resolved into five peaks, three major (I, III, V) and two moderate (II and IV). Profile represents the presence of moderate to low molecular weight components.

DISCUSSION

The genus *Hemibuthus* is distributed in desert and semidesert area of Oriental and Ethiopian regions. This genus is most closely related to *Lychas* Koch, but isolated from the same by its apomorphies carapace entire without vesicle, never provided with subacute spine but a weak subacute nodule is present. Amir *et al.* (1994 a, b, c and d, 2003) discussed the relationships of aedeagus and chemical analysis of venoms of different species of the scorpions from Pakistan.

The new species *Hemibuthus umarii* is described presently, comparing with only monotypic species *H. crassimannus* (Pocock) from Pakistan, Rohri. This species plays sister group relationships with type species but isolated from the same in having its autapomorphies like, the entire body surface smooth, 26 pectinal teeth are present in pectin and in male genitalia the flagellum elongated, flagellar shaped, trunk cylindrical basally dilated, pedicel very flat and sperm spine hook-shaped.

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